

IMPROVEMENT OF KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS OF MA'ARIF VOCATIONAL SCHOOL ON WOMEN'S REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH THROUGH HEALTH PROMOTION

Kusuma Wijaya Ridi Putra¹, Muchamad Indra Ardian², Gerina Dwi Agustina², Anik Amila², Febriany Carla Prameswary², Roghodatul Aisy², Vivi Oktavia²

¹ Lecturer of Kerta Cendekia Nursing Academy, Sidoarjo

² Student of Kerta Cendekia Nursing Academy, Sidoarjo

ABSTRACT

Improvement of knowledge of students at Ma'arif Vocational School regarding women's reproductive health through health promotion is one form of education in the form of counseling aimed at fostering and improving healthy behavior in young women, especially in recognizing women's reproductive health. Implementation of these activities on November 24, 2018 took place at Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo. With the goal is students of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo. Before the implementation of these activities, there is a process of preparing activities for 3 weeks before the activities are carried out, starting from the selection of health counseling materials to the submission of permits to related parties. As an evaluation, the activity was attended by 40 students and 1 teacher, the participants participated in the activity with enthusiasm and conduciveness, the activities could be carried out on time smoothly.

Keywords: Women reproduction, health promotion, student of vocational school.

INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, there are still many young women who pay less attention to the health and hygiene of their reproductive organs, even young women are now far more concerned with outward appearance (face and clothing) than their

reproductive health. Young women still do not know how to properly maintain and care for their reproductive organs and there may still be many who do not yet know the negative effects that arise related to their reproductive organs.

Here it is hoped that the teenagers will increase their knowledge about their reproductive organs, to create healthy young women.

OBJECTIVES

General Purpose

After 60 minutes of health promotion actions, it is hoped that the 3rd grade female students of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo can know and understand widely about women's reproductive health.

Special Purpose

After taking health promotion measures, it is expected that the 3rd grade students of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo can be:

1. Able to know the definition of reproductive health.
2. Able to know the anatomy of the reproductive organs.
3. Able to know how to care for women's reproductive health.
4. Able to know how to maintain the health of reproductive organs.

PLAN OF ACTION

Strategy Plan

The strategy plan implemented, including:

1. Coordinate with the principal of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo to apply for permission to carry out health education or counseling as an activity of the nursing program and to help provide guidance to third grade students of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo.
2. Establish students in the implementation of health education or

counseling to know about women's reproductive health.

3. Contract time with the 3rd grade female students at Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo.
4. Provide health promotion about women's reproductive health.

Implementation

Actions taken in the implementation of these activities, including:

1. Contacted the principal of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo to request permission for activities and gather the third grade students of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo.
2. Prepare a place and counseling media.
3. The 3rd grade female students at Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo received extension materials.

Setting

This activity was carried out at Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo.

Target

Target in this activity is all of the 3rd grade female students at Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The activity starts at 10:30 WIB and ends at 11:30 WIB, the time of health promotion according to planning. Activities carried out at Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo according to the agreement.

The participants who attended were 40 students from the 3rd grade at Ma'arif

Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo along with 1 teacher. Participants seemed conducive and cooperative in the extension activities. 80% of participants can mention the meaning of reproductive health. 75% of participants can mention the anatomy of the female reproductive organs. 90% of participants can mention how to care for their reproductive organs. As many as 80% of participants can follow ways to maintain women's reproductive health.

Activities in the form of health promotion, discussion, question and answer, and distribution of leaflets about women's reproductive health.

The equipment used during the discussion was laptops, power points, videos, and leaflets. The use of very communicative and applicative language in delivering health education, students respond quite well to what has been delivered by students.

Teacher of Ma'arif Vocational School, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo was very enthusiastic and worked very well during the extension.

CONCLUSION

Improvement of knowledge of Ma'arif Vocational School students, Ngaban Road, Tanggulangin, Sidoarjo through health promotion was considered quite successful because almost all students were able to mention the notion of reproductive health (80%), mentioning the anatomy of female reproductive organs (75%), mentioning how to care for reproductive organs (90%), and being able to follow ways maintain women's reproductive health (80%).

REFERENCES

----. (2010). *Kesehatan Reproduksi Remaja*. Retrieved from

<https://belajarpsikologi.com/kesehatan-reproduksi-remaja/> on December 20, 2018.

Glasier, A., & Gebbie, A. (2006). *Keluarga berencana dan kesehatan reproduksi*. Jakarta: EGC.

Manuaba, Gde Bagus Ida. (2004). *Memahami Kesehatan Reproduksi Wanita*. Jakarta: Penerbit Arcan.

Nurachmah, E., Angriani, R., Waugh, A., & Grant, A. (2011). *Dasar-dasar anatomi dan fisiologi*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.

Pertiwi, T.I. (2017). Inilah 8 Cara Menjaga Kesehatan Miss V yang Sering Dilewatkan Wanita. Retrieved from <https://wow.tribunnews.com/2017/10/26/inilah-8-cara-menjaga-kesehatan-miss-v-yang-sering-dilewatkan-wanita?page=4> on December 20, 2018.